

Research

Study on the effects of Multilayered and Multi-Directional Stitched on the Ballistic performance of Kevlar fabric

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Abstract : The aim of this study is increasing inter-yarn friction by using newly developed multi directionally stitched structures for superior ballistic protection of Kevlar fabrics. The para-aramid woven texture was utilized. The structures were in unstitched and sewed structures. In the stitching part used Cotton yarns line the structure in one, two and four bearings though Kevlar® yarn was used to make as it were the four-directionally-sewed structures in six designs with one and two layers. The yarn pull out apparatus was created and the yarn pullout test was performed on single woven texture and sewed structures. Flexural rigidity for fabric is the essential properties, particularly for Ballistic application of superior fabrics and Optical Microscopic test done to watch the progress of the pulled-out portion. Ballistic tests were performed on the structures using 9 mm. In the event that the connected dynamic vitality level is under the yarn breaking expansion, crease in the symmetrical yarns at the fabric structure is right off the bat expelled, and from that point yarn pull out happens in the structure plane and later stage fabric distortion happens in the out-of-plane course of the structure. This wonder proceeds from the outside to the inside layers. In the event that the connected motor vitality level is over the yarn breaking expansion, right off the bat incomplete also, add up to fiber breakages and along these lines

crease evacuation and yarn pull out stages happen. These wonders occur as different yarn disappointment in the external layers and for the most part pleat evacuation also, yarn pull out towards within layers happen. In the two cases, fabric and structure bowing were disregarded. The vitality retention dimension of the sewed structures was somewhat higher than that of the unstitched structures because of the way that some of the vitality was retained to delaminate the interlayer, which was bolted by the sewing yarns. Moreover, the tapered profundity in the sewed structure was low contrasted and that of the unstitched structure.

Keywords: *Ballistic impact, Stitched structure, Yarn pull-out test, Kevlar fabric, Bullet proof vest*

1. Introduction:

Human beings have been confronted with greater threats and disasters since the invention of firearms [1]. In World War I and World War II, thousands of people lost their lives or were injured due to insufficient body protection. After the two world wars, although no large-scale wars occur, the regional wars and conflicts, for example, Iraq war, Syrian conflict and so on, continue to happen, causing numerous deaths [2]. Additionally, due to potential and uncertain threats at any time coming from terrorist incidents, leaders of a country, policemen, and law enforcement officers need to take precautions against such threats. Consequently, it is imperative to develop and manufacture better ballistic body armour to save more lives.

The performance of body armour is largely dependent on used materials. Throughout the whole history of human civilization, people are always trying to seek better materials to protect themselves from injury [3] [4]. With the application of firearms, the traditional protective devices for weapons like swords, spikes, and arrows no longer work for firearms. Many steel plates were initially manufactured as protective shields to firearms. With the development of new materials, alloy and ceramic materials started to be extensively adopted in ballistic body armour. The body armour constructed from the hard plates using these materials is termed as hard body armour which perform satisfactorily in protection. However, it is heavy and bulky. Wearers, who are equipped with such armour, cannot move flexibly in battle, not to mention for daily life protection to policemen or leaders of the country [5-7].

Figure 1: Bullet Proof vest (18th Century)

1.1 Application:

The fibres as candidates used in the ballistic application are mainly divided into three groups [8], aramid fibre, ultra-high molecular weight polyethene (UHMWPE) fibre and poly (p-phenylene benzobisoxazole) (PBO) fibre. Their structures are shown in Figure 2. Aramid is a fibre family containing long benzene ring chains bonded by an amide linkage. The commercial products used as ballistic materials are Kevlar® and Twaron® fibres. UHMWPE, an ultra-high strength polyethene fibre is obtained from the gel-spun manufacturing technology. It is firstly commercialized by Honeywell. Spectra® and Dyneema® are two common commercial names. PBO fibre is a polymer with aromatic heterocyclic rings. [9-11].

Figure 2: The chemical structures (a) Aramid fiber (b) the UHMWPE fiber (c) PBO fiber

1.2 Bulletproof Clothing materials

The tensile properties of these three types of fibre are shown in Table 1. Among these three, PBO fibre is the strongest,[12] but it is likely to be degraded under synergistic action of heat and

moisture. [13] Therefore, the other two types of high-performance fibres, aramid fibres and UHMWPE fibres, are more extensively used in manufacturing soft body armour. [14-16]

Table 1 The tensile properties of the three types of high-performance fibers.

Types of fibre	Commercial products	Density	Tenacity	Modulus	Elongation
		(g/cm ³) (g/cm ³)	(cN/dtex) (cN/dtex)	(cN/dtex) (cN/dtex)	(%)
Aramid fibre	Kevlar® 29	1.44	20.3	490	3.6
	Kevlar® 49	1.45	20.8	780	2.4
	Kevlar® 129	1.44	23.9	700	3.3
	Twaron® 1000	1.44	19.8	495	3.6
	Twaron® 2000	1.44	23	640	3.3
PBO fibre	PBO AS	1.54	42	1300	3.5
	PBO HM	1.56	42	2000	2.5
UHMWPE fibre	Dyneema® SK60	0.97	28	910	3.5
	Dyneema® SK65	0.97	31	970	3.6
	Dyneema® SK75	0.97	35	1100	3.8
	Spectra® 1000	0.97	32	1100	3.3
	Spectra® 2000	0.97	34	1200	2.9

1.3 Properties of Kevlar

Kevlar® was initially created during the 1960s with the compound name of poly-para phenylene terephthalamide; however physicists right up 'til today still don't comprehend why the fiber is so strong. [17] First presented monetarily by Du Pont in 1972, the fiber has comparative rivals in Twaron and Technora.[18][19]

1.4 Characteristics

The resonating normal for Kevlar is its remarkable strength. This solid fiber has had its greatest effect in the ballistics barrier where it's utilized in impenetrable vests. It is more grounded than fiberglass and multiple times more grounded than steel on a pound-for-pound comparison. The high elasticity and modulus are attributes of all the Kevlar strands, with Kevlar 49 and Kevlar 149 appearing significantly higher modulus. [20-22] Kevlar's chains are requested in long parallel

chains, and the key basic accomplishment is the benzene sweet-smelling ring that has a spiral introduction that gives the particle awry and profoundly requested structure that frames pole like structures with a straightforward rehashing backbone.[23] This makes a very solid structure that has a couple of powerless focuses and flaws. The table gave beneath demonstrates the different qualities of Kevlar filaments and were arranged from both the Chemical Economics Handbook and Encyclopedia of Chemical Technology, Notice a lot higher modulus and lower % lengthening from Kevlar 49 and 149. [24-26]

Table 2: Properties of Commercial Aramid Fibers

Fiber type	Density, (g/cm ³)	%Elongation	Modulus, Gpa	Tenacity
Kevlar 29	1.43	3.6	70	20-23
Kevlar 49	1.45	2.8	135	20-26
Kevlar 119	1.44	4.4	55	N/a
Kevlar 129	1.45	3.3	99	N/a
Kevlar 149	1.47	1.5	143	18
Nomex	1.38	22	17	5.8

2. Materials and Methods:

2.1 Materials:

2.1.1 Kevlar Fabric: It's an exclusive material made just by the DuPont™ concoction organization and it comes in two fundamental assortments called Kevlar 29 and Kevlar 49 (different assortments are made for unique applications). The fabric thickness both in twist and weft course is 110tex. In general, the twist and weft densities of the plain Kevlar is around 8.5ends/cm.

Figure 3: Kevlar Fabrics roll

2.1.2 Process of Fabric cutting

Before start sewing, there is a process for cut fabrics from Kevlar fabrics roll. Now describing one by one in details-

a. Electronic Cutter

Used an electronic cutter (especially used for Kevlar Fabrics) to cut the fabrics from the roll and also for turn fabric shape into Sample Size.

Figure 4: Electrical Cutter Machine

b. **Measuring Tape / Scale** : Used to measure and mark the sample size.

c. **Scissor** : This type of special scissor we used to cut tail or extra yarn of our fabrics. Mainly, we used this during the pull out test to cut the tail of pulled yarn.

d. **Sample Size:** The fabric dimension for our study has been selected is (25cm × 25cm).

2.1.3 **Cotton yarn:** Cotton yarn is the ideal backup to 100% cotton fabric and is, in this manner, most regularly utilized in interwoven and sewing. Here, the count of cotton yarn is (40/3).

Figure 5: Cotton Yarn (40/3)

2.1.4 **Industrial Sewing Machine:** Industrial Sewing machine is used here.

Figure 6: Industrial Sewing Machine

2.2 Methods: Sample preparation

1. Select a straight join and a medium line length:

On this machine, join is set by pivoting the lower handle on the correct side of the machine until it fits properly. Continuously set the line with the needle up and out of the Kevlar fabric, since it might move the needle. A straight line is utilized to sew generally creases. The following most regular join is the crisscross, normally used to keep edges from fraying.

Figure 7: Sewing Machine fixed by straight stitch and low stitch length

2. Start with some pieces:

Take a price of Kevlar fabric, try not to utilize a substantial fabric for your first endeavors at machine sewing. In this stitch length, 0 length is so hard to do this work. If others procedure is ok it'll give like figure 8. Here Kevlar stitched in one direction and 2/2 mm distance stitched-

Figure 8 sewing in direction and 2/2 mm distance

3. Line up the fabric under the needle:

Sew with the greater part of the material to one side of the machine; swarming the mass on the correct side can cause wrong sewing.

4. Lower the presser foot onto the fabric:

There is a switch behind or to the side of the needle gets together that raises or brings down the presser foot. On the off chance that you give the fabric a delicate pull while the presser foot down that the machine grasps it pretty immovable. While of sew, the machine utilizes a feed hound under the presser foot to propel the fabric at the right speed. There's no compelling reason to pull the fabric through the machine; truth be told, pulling can twist the needle or harm your venture.

5. Hold the loose ends of the two threads:

For an initial couple of stitches, later have to hold these finishes to keep them from withdrawing into the Kevlar fabrics.

6. Press the foot pedal:

The foot pedal is speed control. In the event that that is the situation, utilize the knee to push it to one side. So this can utilize the equalization wheel on the best, right half of the machine to get the machine turning or to move the needle by hand.

7. Locate the switch catch or switch and attempt it:

It switches the bearing that the machine sustains, so the fabric goes toward you as the machine sews. Toward the finish of a crease, sew a couple of join backward back in the course of the last couple of lines you simply made. This completes the crease and helps shield it from pulling out.

8. Utilize the hand wheel to move the needle to its highest position:

At that point, raise the presser foot. The fabric should haul out effectively. On the off chance that the string destroys back when endeavor to evaluate the fabric, check the needle position.

9. Cut the thread:

On many machines, there is a little score on the back of the post that holds the presser foot. Here, Scissor is used to cur the fabric. Leave a tail reaching out from the machine for next seam.

Figure 9 Scissor to trim the thread

10. Work on sewing:

Take 25/25 cm fabric, from right sides, in the middle started to the edge of 9/9 cm boarder. The seam go 9/9 cm (1mm distance) to 9/9 cm (1mm) from the edge. After this one direction sewed then will go for 2nd direction stitching for finished this sample. As like figure 10 (a)

(a)

(b)

Figure 10 stitched 9/9 cm Kevlar Fabrics (a) 1/1 mm distance (b) 2/2 mm distance

After this sample, make another sample with 2/2 mm distance. In the same way like did before with 1/1 mm distance sample. The fabric is stuck right sides together with the goal that the crease

recompense will finish up within. The "right" side is whichever side of the Kevlar need outwardly when the piece is finished.

Figure 11 stitched 9/9 cm Kevlar Fabrics (a) 3/3 mm distance (b) 6/6 mm distance

11. Move to another piece of the fabrics (two layers):

Utilize the hand wheel at the highest point of the correct side of the machine to move the needle to the highest point of its movement before beginning a crease and again to expel the fabric from the machine toward the finish of a crease. This lifts the needle and enables to move to another territory of the fabric are taking a shot at. On the off chance that the needle isn't at the highest point of its movement, the string may not move when pull on the finishes.

Figure 12 Stitching two layers Kevlar Fabrics (a) 1/1 mm distance (b) 6/6 mm distance

Look for lines on sewing machine showing seam allowance. This is the "Normal" space between the edge of the fabric and the sewing line. For the most part, it should utilize the line at two layers 9/9 cm (1/1mm) and 9/9 cm (6/6 mm). Utilize a ruler measure on either side of the needle

12. Sew a sharp corner:

Need to turn the corner, bring down the needle the whole distance into the fabric. It can utilize the hand wheel to bring down the needle. Raise the presser foot. Leave the needle down, in the fabric. At that point, rotate the fabric to the new position, leaving the needle in it. At last, bring down the presser foot with the fabric in the new position and resume sewing.

13. Focus on the task:

The literature review suggested us, we have to focus on 1/1mm, 2/2mm, 3/3mm or 6/6mm distance Kevlar fabrics in sewing time. This experiment depends on this issue. After this sewing, need to do the ballistic test in their own process.

2.3 Testing Equipment's:

2.3.1 Yarn Pull out Tests: Yarn pull out tests performed on an automated tester analyzer machine. Fabric yarn pullout tests were performed on YG028 modernized tensile tester. Testing standard utilized for yarn pull out was GB/T3923. Pullout tests were performed at a consistent speed of 100mm/min with starting power of 300N to 500N.

Figure 33 Fabric sample testing (a) Sample placed in jaws (b) sample test going on 2/2 dist. sewed sample

2.3.2 Optical Microscopic Test: Optical microscopy is a method utilized to intently see an example through the amplification of a focal point with obvious light. This is the conventional type of microscopy, which was first developed before the eighteenth century is still being used today. An optical magnifying lens, additionally here and there known as a light magnifying lens, utilizes one or a progression of focal points to amplify pictures of little examples with noticeable light. The focal points are put between the example and the watcher's eye to amplify the picture so it very well may be analyzed in more prominent detail.

Figure 14 (a) Optical Microscopic and (b) Observation of 3/3 mm distance after Pullout

2.3.3 Feasibility Testing: Stiffness is a special property of fabric. It is the propensity of fabric to hang onto a rectangular strip of fabric is straddling on a horizontal stage so that it over change, similar to a cantilever, and bends downwards. The horizontal stage of the instrument is bolstered by two side pieces made of plastic or comparable materials. Joined to the instrument is a mirror which empowers the administrator to see both index Lines from an advantageous position.

Figure 15 Feasibility Testing Machine

2.3.4 Ballistic Impact Tester: The Perforation Test is depicted by that a projectile or a completely totally navigating a testing center in the midst of the Impact technique. In the perforation test, the Impact Velocity and the Residual Velocity can be assessed. A square example with the proportion of 25 cm by 25 cm is determined to an under frame with an aperture, of which the width is 15 cm. The outside of the example is verified with a square Steel Frame with an Aperture proportionate to that in the under Frame. The four sides of the example are pressed under the four Strip Steel squares. The four points of the hole are moreover immovably screwed. The effective domain left in the example is around hover with an estimation of 15 cm.

Figure 16: The side view of ballistic Impact Device

3. Results Analysis:

3.1 Yarn pullout tests on plain and stitched fabrics (Single layer): Single and multiple yarns pull out test results from plain fabric, 1/1 mm distance stitched, 2/2 mm distance stitched, 3/3 mm distance stitched, and 6/6 mm distance stitched have been shown in table 3.

Table 3: Yarn pull out test results from Plain and Stitched fabric (Single Layer)

Single and Multiple Yarn Pullout test for Single Layer							
Single Yarn Pull Out		test 1	test 2	test 3	test 4	test 5	Average
1	Plain Fabric	3.4	4.68	4.11	3.02	4.58	3.26
2	1/1 mm dis. Stitched	130.8	117.3	108.7	102.2	131.5	118.1
3	2/2 mm dis. Stitched	71.69	67	87	59	75	71.938
4	3/3 mm dis. Stitched	88.5	103.4	77.86	150.38	88	101.628
5	6/6 mm dis. Stitched	24.74	36.13	60.45	34.67	47.92	40.782
Two Yarn Pull Out		test 1	test 2	test 3	test 4	test 5	Average
1	Plain Fabric	11.8	11.35	11.05	10.85	11.38	11.27
2	1/1 mm dis. Stitched	161.2	162.8	162.7	293	262	208.34
3	2/2 mm dis. Stitched	160.9	130	155	126	109	136.18
4	3/3 mm dis. Stitched	170.15	177.89	99.56	112	142	140.32
5	6/6 mm dis. Stitched	83.62	92.18	144.9	114.1	156.29	118.218
Three Yarn Pull Out		test 1	test 2	test 3	test 4	test 5	Average
1	Plain Fabric	17.38	17.24	18.35	17.49	17.79	17.65
2	1/1 mm dis. Stitched	162.78	393.6	426	263	409.6	330.996
3	2/2 mm dis. Stitched	138.7	144	176	139	155	150.54
4	3/3 mm dis. Stitched	228.86	290	267	208.37	249	248.646
5	6/6 mm dis. Stitched	94.55	141.15	271.88	250.96	197.5	191.208
Four Yarn Pull Out		test 1	test 2	test 3	test 4	test 5	Average
1	Plain Fabric	30.29	28.53	26.15	29.16	28.78	28.57
2	1/1 mm dis. Stitched	409.61	419.6	393.8	401	448.2	434.442
3	2/2 mm dis. Stitched	179.5	167	159	187	179	174.3
4	3/3 mm dis. Stitched	208.37	249.26	360	255.79	309	276.484
5	6/6 mm dis. Stitched	248.92	277.24	206.1	211.3	184.34	225.58

From the above results, it is clear that the yarn pullout force increases by changing the fabric structure from plain fabric, 1/1 mm dist. stitched, 2/2 mm dist. stitched, 3/3 mm dist. stitched and 6/6 mm dist. stitched fabric. Force also increases by pulling multiple numbers of yarns instead of single yarn.

3.2.1 Yarn pullout test results for Plain fabric

In this figure 17 a Single Yarn Pull out test was done of Plain Kevlar Fabric. The deliberate qualities were Yarn Pull out Force and Fabric Displacement (mm). The above table demonstrates that the Force (N) required for one yarn pulled out yarn is higher in one direction contrasted with

warp heading and Fabric Displacement (mm) is additionally demonstrates higher incentive in weft heading for the individual Yarn.

Figure 17-Average Yarn Pull Out from Single and Multiple Yarns (plain fabric)

3.2.2 Yarn pullout test results for 1/1mm Distance Stitched: In figure 18, the curve of single yarn pullout from 1/1 mm distance stitched fabric has been shown. The peak force was higher than the plain fabric and also, it's higher than other stitched structure. This figure shown that, when 1 yarn pulled out the force range is near 110-130 N, for 2 yarns pulled out the force range is near 250-300 N, for 3 yarns pulled out the force range is near 400 N and for the last 4 yarns pulled out result is almost higher than 500 N which is maximum.

Figure 18- Average Yarn Pull Out from Single and Multiple Yarns (1/1mm dist. Stitched)

3.2.3 Yarn pullout test results for 2/2mm Distance Stitched: The curves of the single and multiple yarns of 2/2 mm distance stitched pullout are shown in figure 19. As it shown, in the previous pull out of 1/1 mm distance, in the one pullout moment, it took high time but in the two, three or four yarns pullout time it took much more time and force also.

Figure 19 - Average Yarn Pull Out from Single and Multiple Yarns (2/2mm dist. Stitched)

3.2.4 Yarn pullout test results for 3/3mm Distance Stitched: In the figure 20, we see 1 yarn pullout force is very low and two and three is higher than one yarn pullout. And four yarn pullout is much higher than others. It was almost near 450+ force which is very near to 500 N.

Figure 20- Average Yarn Pull Out from Single and Multiple Yarns (3/3mm dist. Stitched)

3.2.5 Yarn pullout test results for 6/6mm Distance Stitched

In the curves of figure 21, this phenomenon is also explained in terms of stick and slip regions. This fabric stitched is most distance like 6mm gap in both directions. In the carvers as usual 1 yarn pull out need little low force and gradually need more force in two yarn pull out, three yarn pull out and also in four yarn pull out. (most high force).

Figure 21- Average Yarn Pull Out from Single and Multiple Yarns (6/6 mm dist. Stitched)

3.3 Yarn pullout tests on plain and stitched fabrics (Two layers)

Table 4: Yarn pull out test results from Plain and Stitched fabric (Two layers)

Single and Multiple Yarn Pullout test for Double Layer							
Single Yarn Pull Out		test 1	test 2	test 3	test 4	test 5	Average
1	Plain Fabric	3.4	4.68	4.11	3.02	4.58	3.26
2	1/1 mm dis. Stitched	244.97	256.8	275	248	347	274.354
3	6/6 mm dis. Stitched	162.78	318.75	129.14	358.37	255.9	244.988
Two Yarn Pull Out		test 1	test 2	test 3	test 4	test 5	Average
1	Plain Fabric	11.8	11.35	11.05	10.85	11.38	11.27
2	1/1 mm dis. Stitched	472.27	437.8	440	419.3	479	449.674
3	6/6 mm dis. Stitched	352.46	375.5	368.83	289.7	347.2	346.738
Three Yarn Pull Out		test 1	test 2	test 3	test 4	test 5	Average
1	Plain Fabric	17.38	17.24	18.35	17.49	17.79	17.65
2	1/1 mm dis. Stitched						
3	6/6 mm dis. Stitched	379.2	353.45	317.1	390	398	367.55
Four Yarn Pull Out		test 1	test 2	test 3	test 4	test 5	Average
1	Plain Fabric	30.29	28.53	26.15	29.16	28.78	28.57
2	1/1 mm dis. Stitched						
3	6/6 mm dis. Stitched	501.15	480.6	500	500	498	495.95

From the above results it is clear that the yarn pullout force increases by changing the fabric structure from plain fabric, two layers of 1/1 mm dist. stitched and 6/6 mm dist. stitched fabric. Force also increases by pulling multiple numbers of yarns instead of single yarn. It can be seen from the table there is not much difference in plain and stitched fabrics. But most important thing, in 1/1 mm distance stitched three and four yarn pull out the force (N) was very high which is higher than 500 N. So that's reason for no result of this part.

3.4 Yarn pullout test compared with all structure:

Table 3- Comparative study of yarn pull out Force from Single and Multiple Yarn in all structure compared with Plain Kevlar Fabric

Yarn Pull Out Force Average Comparison	Warp Direction			
	1 Yarn	2 Yarn	3 Yarn	4 Yarn
	Force (N)	Force (N)	Force (N)	Force (N)
Plain Kevlar Fabrics	3.29	11.31	17.70	28.63
1/1 distance Stitched	118.10	208.34	330.99	434.44
2/2 distance Stitched	71.94	136.18	150.54	174.30

3/3 distance Stitched	101.63	140.32	248.65	276.49
6/6 distance Stitched	40.79	118.22	191.21	225.58
1/1 two layers Distance Stitched	274.35	449.69	>500	>500
6/6 two layers Distance Stitched	244.99	346	367.55	495.95

From the above results of the comparative study of yarn pullout force from single and multiple yarns in all structure compared with plain Kevlar fabric and it is clear that the yarn pullout force increases by changing. The fabric structure from plain fabric, 1/1 mm dist. stitched, 2/2 mm dist. stitched, 3/3 mm dist. stitched, 6/6 mm dist. stitched two layers 1/1 mm dist. stitched and two layers 6/6 mm dist. stitched fabric. Force also increases by pulling multiple numbers of yarns instead of single yarn. In figure 22, if we go step by step, we will see high force for 1/1 distance stitched. In this graph for 1 yarn pull out got 118.10 (N), 2 yarns pullout got 208.34 (N), 3 yarns pullout 330.99(N) and 4 yarns pullout 434.44 (N) which is a very good result. In another way, in two layers 1/1 mm dist. stitched we got just only 1 yarn and 2 yarns pullout result. But for 3 yarns and 4 yarns, it was out of force. That means higher than 500 (N)

Figure 22 Yarn Pullout force average comparison with plain Kevlar fabric

3.5 Optical Microscopic Result Observation

Done this optical Microscopic test because of known to find out the difference between before and after the Pull out the test. In the below, there are some differences-

3.5.1 Yarn Pull out Observation of 1/1 mm distance

In the 1/1 distance Yarn Pull out, before the pull out there is usually there is no change as in figure 23 (a). Because as an experiment this is 1st sample 1/1 mm distance which is very narrow and

close. In this next (b) there is shown edge part of 1/1 mm dist. Sewed, it also before sewed. Next, there is a figure (c) in that place little clarified about breakage things. And in the figure (d) there pulled out 2 yarn together and got a good change after the pullout on the fabrics. In the pullout time, the yarn wasn't come out after the force of the machine. Which is a very good side for this 1/1 mm yarn pulled out. And most of the time in 1/1 mm yarn pull out, it didn't take that yarn properly. So that in 1 yarn pull out and 2 yarns pull out were an almost same condition when pull out happened. But in figure 34 (e) and (f) we gave more force, it was 500 N that was the reason for made a massive change after pulled out.

(a) Before Pull out 1/1 mm sewed fabric
(Middle Part)

(b) Before Pull out 1/1 mm sewed fabric
(Edge Part)

(c) After 1 yarn pulled out (down side)

(d) After 2 yarns pulled out (down side)

(e) After 3 yarns pulled out (Top Side)

(f) After 4 yarns pulled out (top side)

Figure 23 Yarn Pull out Observation of 1/1 mm distance

3.5.2 Yarn Pull out Observation 2/2 distance:

In the 2/2 distance Yarn Pull out, This is 1mm more distance than the previous sample. But the result was almost the same. It wasn't pull out the yarn because strongly connected with the kevlar after sewed. So the result of during pulled out it breaks the yarn at the edge of the sewed. In figure 24 (a) and (b) shown before pulled out fabric. In the next figure (c) and (d) we see there is little gap inside the fabric because of yarns friction at (c) and one yarn breakage after two yarns pulled out. In this figure 24 (e) and (f), No hairiness before the pullout test. But after pull out, it was totally changed with hairiness. Because when pullout happened, it gave lots of pressure on the pullout part or yarns side. So that it makes hairiness in that part.

(a) After sewed 2/2mm (middle side)

(b) before 2/2mm pulled out (edge side)

(c) After 1 yarn pulled out

(d) After 2 yarns pulled out

(e) Hairless before Pull out

(a) Hairiness after Pull Out

Figure 24 Yarn Pull out Observation 2/2 distance

3.5.3 Yarn Pull out Observation 3/3 distance:

In the two figures of 25 (a) and (b), we are getting after pullout test have some change inside on the fabric. We see there is some gap in the figure (b) and which thing happens after the pullout test. There is shown more pictures yarn-wise. Because we know in pull out process if we want to get a good result, we need to pull out at least four yarns. Like this way, In figure (c) and (d) there pulled out one and two yarns gradually And also we see in (e) and (f) three and four yarns together pulled out. For this figure (e) and (f), the force was very high. Max 500 N. And as in Figure (f) we see there is massive change after pulled out test. In this figure 25 (g) and (h), No hairiness before the pullout test after sewed fabric. But after pulled out it was totally changed with hairiness. Because when pullout happened, it gave lots of pressure on the pullout part or yarns side. So that it makes hairiness in that part.

(a) After sewed 3/3 mm (middle side)

(b) After Pulled out 3/3 mm sewed fabric

(c) After 1 yarn pulled out

(d) After 2 yarns pulled out

(e) After 3 yarns pulled out

(f) After 4 yarn pulled out

(g) Hairless before pullout test

(h) Hairiness after Pull Out

Figure 25 Yarn Pull out Observation 3/3 distance

3.5.4 Yarn Pull out Observation 6/6 distance:

In this figure 26 (a) and (b), we can see that huge change after the pullout the test in the figures. In the others sewed fabric as 1/1 mm distance or 2/2 mm distance we saw force didn't take the yarns pulled but in 6/6 mm distance yarns can pulled little easily. And created a big gap on the fabrics. In figure 26 (c) and (d) we can see the difference in 1 yarn pulled out place make a 1 yarn gap and 2 yarns pulled out place make 2 yarns gap. And also in (e) and (f) sample of fabric, there changed is more clear than two yarn and one yarn pulled out.

(a) After sewed 6/6 mm (middle side)

(b) After pullout Hairiness

(c) 1 yarn pulled out

(d) 2 yarns pulled out

(e) 3 yarns pull out

(f) 4 yarns pull out

Figure 26 Yarn Pull out Observation 6/6 distance.

3.5.5 Yarn Pull out Observation of 1/1 distance (Two Layers)

In this figure 27 observation of two layers 1/1 mm distance, we can see (a) sample which is the middle side of the 1/1 mm two layer. Last 4 sample was 1/1, 2/2, 3/3 and 6/6 one layer fabric but in two layers observation is little different from the previous sample. In the (b) sample we see the edge side of the sample which is before pulled out the test. And in this sample (c) there is 1 yarn pulled out observation but we see the edge side has not that much different and in the sample (d) two yarn pulled out there was little change happened.

(a) before 1/1 pull out (middle side)

(c) before 1/1mm pulled out (edge side)

(c) 1 yarn pulled out

(d) 2 yarn pulled out

Figure 27 Yarn Pull out observation of 1/1 distance (Two Layers)

3.5.6 Yarn Pull out Observation of 6/6 distance (Two Layers)

In this figure 28, (a) We can see before 6/6 pulled out for match or observation with after pullout the test. And in (b) one of a sample of after pulled out. After this sample in (c) and (d) we can see one yarn pulled out and two yarns pulled out a sample. But more clearly changed is in the sample (d). Because it was pulled up but didn't come to the yarn as before others. Then in the sample (e)

and (f), we see the massive change after pulled out. Mainly in sample (f), because of 500 N force with four yarns from the back and four yarns from the front were pulled up together.

(a) before 6/6 pull out

(b) After 6/6 mm pull out

(c) 1 Yarn pulled out

(d) 2 yarns pulled out

(e) Three yarn pull out

(f) Four yarn pull out

Figure 28 Yarn Pull out Observation of 6/6 distance (Two Layers)

3.5.7 Yarn Breakage

In figure shown 29, we see some yarn breakage on below figure basically for 1/1, 2/2 and 1/1 two layers' distance pull out test time.

1. It's happened because of the Kevlar yarn was attached with sewing thread.

2. Which Yarn we pulled out but didn't come out, that one is fixed with stitch part very tightly and Maximum time it's happened because of this.

(a)The pullout from 1/1mm stitched

(b)The pullout from 2/2 mm stitched

(c) The pullout from 3/3mm stitched

(d)Pullout from 1/1mm stitched

(e) Two Layer 1/1mm stitched

(f) Two Layer 6/6mm stitched

Figure 29 Yarn Breakages

3.6 Fabric Flexibility /Stiffness

Figure 30 - Fabric Stiffness observation from different Area

Table 4- Fabric stiffness/ Flexibility Test Result

Structure					Mean					Mean
	S 1	S 2	S 3	S 4	Value (LC)	S 1	S 2	S 3	S 4	Value (LS)
Plain Kevlar Fabric	7.54	7.29	7.36	7.65	7.46	14.19	13.97	14.28	14.18	14.15
1/1 mm Distance Stitched	6.22	6.26	6.23	6.29	6.25	12.45	12.52	12.33	12.61	12.48
2/2 mm Distance Stitched	5.74	5.63	5.78	5.58	5.68	11.49	11.27	11.35	11.23	11.33
3/3 mm Distance Stitched	6.22	6.11	6.25	6.13	6.17	12.44	12.22	12.27	12.41	12.33
6/6 mm Distance Stitched	6.37	6.02	6.14	6.33	6.21	12.75	12.05	12.54	12.71	12.51
1/1 mm Distance Stitched (Two Layers)	9.09	9.15	9.56	9.02	9.20	18.19	18.26	18.25	18.15	18.21
6/6 mm Distance Stitched (Two layers)	8.59	8.65	8.43	8.55	8.55	17.42	17.57	17.38	17.48	17.46
*LC=Bending Length (Mean Value (LC) in the Graph)										
*LS=Length Extension (Mean Value (LS) in the Graph)										

From the above mentioned, Length Extension (LS) is All Over stitched (25 cm × 25 cm) 1/1mm, 2/2 mm, 3/3 mm, 6/6 mm, two layers 1/1mm and two layers 6/6 mm nearly demonstrated straight information. In any case, in the result of two layers got indicated much higher length expansion rate than that of a single length of this structure. On the Contrary, Bending Length (LC) additionally indicates for Plain Kevlar fabric 7.46%, 1/1 mm distance stitched 6.25%, 2/2 mm distance stitched 5.68%, 3/3 mm distance stitched 6.17%, 6/6 mm distance 6.21%, two-layer 1/1 mm distance stitched 9.20% and two layers 6/6 distance stitched 8.55% respectively contrast with Plain Fabrics. On the off chance that if the Bending Length of the Fabric is more than Fabric Stiffness is more and if less stiffness is less. So, from the above information, it is very obvious to us that 1/1 mm, 2/2mm,3/3mm and 6/6 mm also two layers Kevlar has less stiffness rate contrast with other and consider as a decent Drape in genuine Ballistic Protection. Be that as it may, more stiffness impacts the Fabric Deformation and Sheds Light on the instrument of Fabric deformation. As for sewing on Kevlar fabric increase, the yarn or fiber dimensions leads to fabric stiffness.

3.7 Ballistic Impact Results

3.7.1 Plain Kevlar Fabric

A plain single-layer fabric uncovered by perforation Impact test in this part. In order to survey the Energy Absorption limit of a plain single-layer Fabric at different elements of Inter-yarn Friction at a comparable impact Velocity and Residual Velocity ought to be produced which is conveying in the outline above. In the table 7, it is entirely observable to us that under average Mean Value is 132.19% of Impart speed in plain Kevlar fabric the average energy absorption rate is 7.23 (J) during the test.

Table 5 Ballistic Impact result of Plain Kevlar Fabric

Structure	Plain Kevlar Fabric		
Data parameters	Impact Velocity (m/s)	Residual Velocity (m/s)	Calculated Energy Loss (J)
Sample 1	157.6	128.6	8.2998
Sample 2	143.6	115.2	7.34992
Sample 3	122.6	84.5	7.89051
Sample 4	101.8	56.5	7.17099
Sample 5	91.5	63.7	4.31456
Sample 6	151.9	124.8	7.49857
Sample 7	156.3	127.8	8.09685
Mean Value	132.19	100.157	7.23

Figure 31 The differentiation Graph of the impact velocity and residual velocity of Plain Kevlar Fabric

3.7.2 3/3 mm distance stitched Kevlar Fabric

In table-8 portraying that, Energy absorption increased high than of plain Kevlar fabric which shows indicates less layers of fabrics requires during the procedure of Ballistic materials. It is entirely observable to us that under average Mean Value is 155% of Impact Speed In on the 3/3 mm distance stitched and the average energy absorbing rate is 18.01(J) during the test because of low inter yarn Friction between yarns.

Table 6 Ballistic Impact result of 3/3 mm distance stitched Kevlar Fabric

Structure	3/3 mm distance stitched Kevlar Fabric		
Data parameters	Impact Velocity (m/s)	Residual Velocity (m/s)	Calculated Energy Loss (J)
Sample 1	157.5	70.8	19.79361
Sample 2	153.1	Did not go through	-
Sample 3	155.3	88.8	16.23265
Sample 4	154.1	102.7	13.19952
Mean Value	155	87.433	18.013

Figure 32 the differentiation Graph of the impact velocity and residual velocity of 3/3 mm distance stitched

3.7.3 6/6 mm distance stitched Kevlar Fabric

In the structure, Perforation test is depicting that during Impact Velocity (m/s), the Residual Velocity (m/s) is impacted in an expected way. The Energy Absorption limit of this structure is amazingly pivotal than that of plain Kevlar Fabric and 6/6 mm distance Kevlar fabric. From the table, we can see that during the Impacted Velocity 154.68 m/s under 0.002 kg mass projectile, the shot/bullet couldn't go through the fabric which gives extraordinary hint in our advancement territory with ensuring high Energy absorbing limit as the structure has a higher inter yarn friction because of stitched part.

Structure	6/6 mm distance stitched Kevlar Fabric		
Data parameters	Impact Velocity (m/s)	Residual Velocity (m/s)	Calculated Energy Loss (J)
Sample 1	156.3	99.8	14.470
Sample 2	155.2	-	
Sample 3	152	113.9	10.131
Sample 4	155.2	104.3	13.209
Sample 5	155.3	99.3	14.258
Sample 6	155.2	120.5	9.567

Sample 7	153	110.9	11.110
Sample 8	155.2	103.2	13.437
Mean Value	154.68	107.41	12.311

Table 7 Ballistic Impact result of 6/6 mm distance stitched Kevlar Fabric

Figure 33 the differentiation Graph of the impact velocity and residual velocity of 6/6 mm distance stitched Kevlar Fabric

3.7.4 Ballistic Perforated Impact Test in Structure Wise

In the pictures of (A), (B) and (C) describing the effects of the ballistic impact of plain Kevlar fabric and between yarns prompts to the less vitality assimilation along these lines cause simple go of slug through the objective. The impacts of ballistic impact are plainly noticeable on the pictures. In the case of (D), (E) and (F) pictures 3/3 mm distance stitched structure unmistakably depicting us the vitality ingestion capacity than that of the plain structure. And in this structure affected by every direction after the ballistic impact. In the 3/3 mm distance stitched structure picture (F) the absorption rate was high and in some cases this structure absorb all the energy and prevent the bullet pass through the sewed fabric. And in the picture of (G), (H) and (I) pictures of 6/6 mm distance stitched structure depicting high retaining limit among all the structure which is unmistakable in the ballistic effect information table of this structure. This occurs due to the higher and even inter friction among the yarn with the bullet were constrained after effect that without a doubt demonstrated the higher energy retaining limit as in pictures.

Figure 34: Ballistic Perforated Impact Test

4. Discussion & Conclusion:

Multilayered and Multidirectional-stitched ballistic structures have been created also, their ballistic exhibitions contrasted and those of unstitched structures. High-and low-thickness fabrics

were utilized to make the ballistic structures. The Kevlar fabric destroys out the test was created to get it the ballistic wonders in sewed structures. Single and various yarn pullouts were done on both single fabrics also, just single yarn pull-outs made on sewed structures. It is comprehended that high-thickness fabric indicates higher pull out powers contrasted and those of low-thickness texture. Sewing builds the pullout power in the structure thought about with that of a single fabric.

All structures were affected by one kind of shot in any case, at changed rates. It was uncovered that the particular energy assimilation dependent on the harmed layers is marginally better in the sewed structure contrasted and that of the unstitched structure. This is a direct result of the sewing yarn and sewing frictional powers produced on every fabric layer. In this manner, the all-out vitality could be consumed by the sewing yarn itself in the out-of-plane heading of the structure and the sewing frictional powers in the in-plane heading of the fabric layer.

1. After the pulled out test it's clear that the yarn pullout force increase by changing the fabric from plain fabric, 1/1 mm distance stitched, 2/2 mm distance stitched, 3/3 mm distance stitched, 6/6 mm distance stitched and also two layers of 1/1 and 6/6 mm stitched. If we see pull out test average result of plain and stitched fabric, there is for plain fabric 1 yarn to 4 yarns average was 3.26, 11.27, 17.65 and 28.57. Then 1/1 mm distance stitched result was 118.1, 208.34, 330.99 and 434.44. After this 2/2 distance stitched result was 71.93, 136.18, 150.54 and 174.3. In the next 3/3 mm distance stitched average result is 101.63, 140.32, 248.65 and 276.4. And for single layer last 6/6 mm distance stitched result is 40.78 for 1 yarn, 118.22 for 2 yarn, 191.21 for 3 yarns and 225.58 for 4 yarn pull out.

If we see the result of two layers it gave 500 (N) force for 1/1 mm distance pulled out. And the result was for one yarn 274.35 and two yarn was 346.74. And the left three and four yarns pull out result we didn't get because of force limitation. Another way, two layers 2/2 mm distance result was 244.98, 346.73, 367.55 and almost 495.9. But you can tell for this it was higher than 500 (N) force. So after this pullout test 1/1 mm distance stitched shows us the good result as we see in yarn pull out force average comparison. Fabric displacement in multiple-end pull-out showed high fabric displacement compared to that of the single pull-out.

As the expected result was improved inter yarn friction of Kevlar fabrics for improved ballistic performance using Multilayered and Multidirectional-stitched with lightweight. And in this case, we have some good result for 1/1mm distance stitched and also 2/2 mm distance stitched which can give us to increase the inter-yarn friction without much affecting the weight of soft body armor as out expected result.

2. In the optical Microscopic observation, which can show the progress on the pulled out portion. If we see 1/1 mm dist. the sewed portion after pulled out there is not that much change inside the sewed portion. But had some change edge side of the pulled out yarn. Sometimes it broke the yarn. Then for the 2/2 mm dist. stitched we got some hairiness after the pull out inside of the sewing section. In the next, 3/3 mm dist. stitched we got some yarn pulled out and created gap inside the fabric also got hairiness. And for 6/6 mm dist. stitched we got massive change after the pull out. We got yarn pulled out and change of the yarns of sewing. But two layers pulled it was not that much changeable because of force limitation.
3. In the experiment, Numerical relations have been found between fabric stiffness in difference sewing structure. Fabric stiffness of a fabric is the fundamental properties, especially for Ballistic Application of prevalent fabrics. Stiffness is the main thing among the most and large used parameters to condemn Bending Rigidity and fabric Handling. So as in test, found the result Bending Length (LC) for plain Kevlar fabric 7.46%, 1/1 mm distance stitched 6.25%, 2/2 mm distance stitched 5.68%, 3/3 mm distance stitched 6.17%, 6/6 mm distance 6.21% and for Two layers 1/1 mm distance and 6/6 mm distance gradually 9.20% and 8.55%. After this test, we can tell that 2/2 mm distance stitched is less than others bending length which is better and performed good for this experiment.
4. In our study, we used the perforation test is for the most part to understand energy absorption ratio from the variation of imparting Velocity and Residual Velocity. In the plain fabric, we found energy absorption increase rate is 25.74% before stitched the yarn. But in the 3/3 mm distance stitched fabric we found increase rate of 43.74% and for 6/6 mm distance stitched fabric energy absorption increase rate is 30.49%. So, under the impact velocity range from 100 m/s to 160 m/s, the full energy could be consumed by the sewed part of the fabric and frictional force in the in-plane course of the fabric layer. That means, the fabric sewed structure with higher inter-yarn friction presents higher resistance to the

projectile and if we reduce the stitched distance of the fabric it will impact energy more successfully. In this perforation test, 3/3 mm distance stitched on Kevlar fabric found good ballistic after the parameter test.

Sewed structures have low tapered profundity analyzed with that of unstitched structures. This is on the grounds that the sewing yarn makes the structure firm and decreases the auxiliary misshapen in the out-of-plane heading. The best outcomes are accomplished in four-directionally-sewed structures where the sewing yarn is 1/1 distance Stitched.

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